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“WHEN COMMUNICATION FAILS”

For weeks, the air had been heavy and unmoving. So, when the first drops hit the roofs of Barangay San Isidro, people stepped outside and stretched their arms as if welcoming the cool air. Children also happily played on the wet ground.

Inside the municipal disaster office, Carlo watched the radar. It indicated a low-pressure area within a normal range. It was his first year as a DRRM officer. Carlo trusted systems, thresholds, and protocols because that was what he had been trained to do. He believed communication should be accurate before it was released. Anything less felt irresponsible to him. When her assistant, Liza, asked whether they should alert the barangay, Carlo replied. “Not yet, we wait for confirmation.”

Outside, the rain thickened. By afternoon, field reports began to change. Carlo scanned the data through the computer screen. Numbers were still within acceptable limits, but only barely. On the DRRM’s social media page, people started to flood with questions about evacuation. However, Carlo hesitated. If he warned too early, people might panic or, worse, stop trusting future advisories. If he waited, he could be sure. So, he waited.

The river in Barangay San Isidro overflowed before sunset. Water rushed through narrow streets, faster than anyone expected. People scrambled in their homes, carrying what they could. This time, Carlo activated the siren. However, the flood had already entered homes. The warning came, but it arrived too late.

Days later, Carlo walked through the barangay. He could see mud clinging to the house walls. Broken furniture that was damaged by the flood is laid outside. He stopped his walk when he saw Mang Ruel. “We waited for the announcement,” the old man said to Carlo quietly. “We thought you would tell us when to leave.” Carlo panicked. He opened his mouth, but he could not utter a single word. The conversation felt like a confrontation to him.

That night, he reviewed everything. He looked at data, reports, and the timeline. Technically, he had not been wrong. But something in him resisted that conclusion. He replayed the moment people started asking about evacuation advisories. Then it hit him. He had answered with silence. That was when he understood that communication in disasters was not just about certainty. It was about action. People were not asking for perfect data. The residents were seeking guidance amid uncertainty. After long hours of contemplation, Carlo whispered to himself. “By waiting to be completely right, I had failed to be useful”.

A week later, another storm formed. Barangay San Isidro is one of the areas to experience the storm. Carlo stared at the screen. The data remained incomplete, and the forecasts remained uncertain. He shifted his gaze to the siren control. In his mind, the voices of people asking for evacuation advisories replayed. He imagined the same question being asked again. This time, he picked up the microphone. "Advisory," Carlo's voice echoed through the speakers stationed in each designated area in the barangay. "Possible rapid flooding. Pre-emptive evacuation is recommended."

It wasn't perfect the way he would want it. But it was clear and timely. This time, Carlo understood that in disaster communication, the right message at the right time can save lives and property.

